

THE VIEWPOINTS OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGERS ON EDUCATIONAL PLANNING IN TURKEYⁱ

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Abstract:

The Phenomenology Design was used in the present study which aims to determine the viewpoints of educational managers on how much the educational planning processes are successful in Turkey. The Phenomenology Design is one of the Qualitative Research Methods. In recent studies that aim to investigate the relation between development and education, it has been reported that the knowledge, skills and attitudes acquired with the help of education increase the incomes of the individuals and the country. The behaviors acquired by individuals with the help of education increase the productivity in economy. Planning is defined as a design process which will take an institution or an individual to a certain goal from the present position. Educational planning may be defined as a basic roadmap to cover the needs of the society and to realize the aims of it. Educational planning is not only a topic that interests the Ministry of Education. This is a common issue of ministries responsible for planning, economy and society. The Study Group was selected with the Maximum Variety Sampling Method, which is one of the Purposeful Sampling Methods. Ten principals (n=10) working in Ankara were selected as the sample of the study. Three main themes, which were developed by the author of the study, were used in the data collection tool. These themes were Planning Concept, Planning Activities, and Application of Educational Planning. A "Semi-Structured Interview Form", which consisted of the sub-themes of these main themes, was also used as the data collection tool. Detailed interviews were made with the participants to collect the study data. The interview records were analyzed by the author of the study, and were then converted into text on computer. It was determined in the study that the participants knew the planning concept, and were aware of using it as a management process. It was also determined that the participants did not have adequate knowledge on educational planning concept. However, it is also possible to claim that the managers that had postgraduate education had knowledge on educational planning as well. It was observed that educational planning was generally made in Teachers Board

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at schools in school management. It was determined that educational managers point out the importance of an applicable educational planning.

Keywords: education managers, education planning, phenomenology design, planning approach, concept of planning

1. Introduction

Education may be defined as a process that aims to develop an individual in all aspects. While individuals develop in all aspects, they also develop the society. In addition, the place of education in economic development cannot be denied. The effect of planning on education was first mentioned by classical economist Adam Smith, T. R. Malthus, and D. Ricardo. Then, A. Marshall conducted studies reporting that as the educational level increased so did the economic growth. The science of economy developed through years, and the well-developed and developing countries became interested in planned development. A good development may facilitate greatly the interpretation of the existing conditions in an accurate manner, benefiting the opportunities in a country in a realistic manner, determining the results of each choice, and thus, facilitating accurate decision making and agreement between the decisions made. Turkey is one of these countries, and the 1961 Constitution brought with it the necessity of preparing a Development Plan with an interval of five years.

In studies that deal with the relation between development and education, it was reported that the knowledge, skills and attitudes acquired with the help of education increased the income level of the country and the individuals. It was also reported in previous studies that the factors that affected the development of a country were the increase in employment followed by the increase in the educational level, the increase in the capital inputs, furthering in knowledge level (technology) and the social effect caused by market expansion. The behaviors acquired by individuals through education increase the productivity in economy (Karakütük, 2016). According to Adem (1997), a balanced distribution is only possible with a good planning to cover the educational needs with scarce resources. In this context, the planning in economy is reflected in education, and thus, educational planning is realized.

Planning may be defined as the full and efficient use of the resources (materials and human) at hand. Karakütük (2017) defined planning as a design process, and as an action that would take the individual or the institution from a certain place to a planned target. Adem (2008) defined educational planning as the search for options that will be provided by the future, determining the targets and changing responsibilities, attracting the areas that may produce problematic outcomes and imbalanced issues, and produce solutions for possible problems. Bursalıoğlu (1994) defined it as the search for the system and especially as the management of education system through operational research.

With educational planning, it is possible to draw a roadmap that will take the institutions to the desired targets from the present point and that will ensure a balanced distribution of the resources. Educational planning may be defined as the basic road in realizing the targets and covering the needs of the society and students. With the broadest meaning, educational planning is the application of reasonable and organized analysis technique on educational process for the purpose of making education become a more powerful and efficient tool in realizing the targets and covering the needs of the society and students (Coombs, 1973).

Educational planning works started with industrial plans in 1930s in Turkey, and were included in the Development Plans in the Constitution in 1960. In 2000s, strategic planning works were started. Before 1960, "social aims" were not targeted in the planning works that were proposed by international organizations and institutions; however, after 1960, economic and social problems were considered together, and it was decided to handle both sides of planning together (Karakütük, 2001). Educational planning has an important place within the social targets in development plans. In development plans, the importance of education as a public property and its effect in development were emphasized more. However, despite this, a planned development was not achieved in raising the trained manpower needed by the country, and adequate resources were not allocated for the financing of education (Altundemir, 2012).

According to Adem (2008), general targets of educational planning are collected under the following titles; quantitative, qualitative, educational management, and financing of education. In order to increase the educational capacity, the factors like pedagogy, population, and geographical, economic, social issues etc. must be investigated. Quantitative planning must include the factors like the population of schools (registers, losses, graduates), teachers, the number of auditors, and their training, classrooms, laboratories, workshops, and classroom materials. Qualitative planning must include the factors like the preparation of educational targets, the contents, and educational methods, programs, raising of educational staff, teacher-student and auditor-teacher relations, guidance and research, course books, and other auxiliary materials. Educational management must include management at national, regional and local level, management and auditing of schools, personnel issues, administrative structure and methods; while the financing of education must include the determination of the expenses (unit cost per student, the cost of investment for additional capacity per student, the cost of investment per teacher, unit cost per graduates). Financial resources (national, regional, local and foreign resources -if any-, and technical aids), the distribution of the expenses (correct investment, capital formation and transfer, social investments on students, scholarships and educational loans) must also be determined as well (Adem, 2008). Educational planning is not a situation that merely involves the participation of the ministry of education. It is something related with the ministry that is responsible for planning, and the ministries that are responsible for economy and society; in fact, it is related with the whole of the society. In other words, this is the problem of the whole society. The aim of the present

study was to determine the viewpoints of the educational managers on how much the educational planning processes in Turkey was successful in recent years.

2. Material and Methods

The Phenomenology Design was used in the study. In Phenomenology, the researchers focus on phenomena with which they are familiar but do not have a detailed insight (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006). This research method borrows the experiences of the individuals for the purpose of defining and interpreting their own experiences (Jasper, 1994; Miller, 2003). Phenomenology focuses on human experiences formed by social reality in order to understand the social reality (Ersoy, 2016). In the phenomenology analysis of a qualitative study, the general definition of a phenomenon is made by making use of the experiences of individuals through individual statements (Patel, 2002; Baker, 1992). Meanwhile, in phenomenology analysis, individual experiences are investigated in detail, and the formation of individual perceptions of the participants are described (Smith and Eatough, 2007).

2.1 The Study Group

The Study group consisted of ten education administrators. The education administrators were selected with Maximum Variety Sampling Method, which is one of the Purposeful Sampling Methods. Purposeful Sampling Method is the selection of the participants that are rich in information in terms of the aim of the study for the purpose of conducting a detailed research. Maximum Variety Sampling is the formation of the sampling from similar situations within itself related with the problem (Büyüköztürk, 2016). Three of the participants were women, and seven were men. Four education administrators worked at primary schools, three worked at secondary schools, three worked at high schools. Maximum variety was ensured among the participants in terms of seniority and school management steps.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

The three themes that were developed by the author of the study (the planning concept, the planning activities, and the application of the educational planning); and the "Semi-Structured Interview Form", which consisted of sub-themes of these were used as the data collection tool in the study; and detailed interviews were made with the education administrators. In detailed interviews, the researcher does not only seek the answer of certain problems, but also tries to discover the personal viewpoints and interpretation mechanisms of the participant on the subject matter (Şekerciler, 2015). The questions in the interview form were sent to specialists working in the field of educational economy and educational planning, and after the required corrections were made, the form was given the final shape.

2.3 The Analysis of the Data

The records of the interviews were analyzed by the researcher, and were converted into text by the author of the study on computer. In addition, the interview records were also converted into text by a specialist again, and the consistency of the two texts were checked by the author of the study. The qualitative data obtained in the study were analyzed by the author of the study by using the Content Analysis Method. The data were grouped under certain themes and reported. In this study, education administrators were coded as A1, A2...

3. Findings

When the demographical structure of the education administrators who participated in the study were analyzed, it was seen that three of them were graduated from postgraduate degree, and seven were graduated from undergraduate programs. Four of the participants had a seniority of 1-5 years, three had a seniority of 5-10 years, and three of them had a seniority of 10+ years. Three of the education administrators who were interviewed were women, and seven were men. Four of the participants were managers at primary schools, three were managers at secondary schools, and three were managers at high schools. In addition, two of these managers worked at private educational institutions, and eight of them worked at public schools.

3.1 The Viewpoints on Planning Concept

It is possible to claim that the viewpoints of the managers who participated in the study on educational planning were at an adequate level. These viewpoints were mentioned with statements like *“designing the future”* (Y1, Y8), *“a pre-defined route”* (A3, A5, A6), *“achieving the targets”* (A2), *“using the resources in an efficient way”* (A10), *“the route followed step-by-step”* (A4), *“designing the stages to proceed towards the targeted goal from your present place”* (A9), *“running the works with the guidance of a program by using the available data and resources”* (A7). Participant (A7) defined planning as *“running the works with the guidance of a program by using the available data and resources”*; while participant (A9) defined it as *“a kind of designing the future. Designing the stages to proceed towards the targeted goal from your present place”*.

3.2 The Viewpoints on the Educational Planning Concept

The viewpoints of the managers who were included in the study on educational planning were as follows; *“determining where to reach from your present position in education”* (A7), *“ensuring that teachers work in a planned manner”* (A1, A5, A10), *“acting in accordance with the plans provided by the Ministry of National Education”* (MoNE) (A8, A4), *“distributing the classes and subjects to teachers and auditing the functioning”* (A6, A3), calculating the inputs and outputs in order to reach the goals in education by the state (A2), *“running the works in an academic year within a certain program”* (A9). It is possible to claim that the education administrators who are postgraduate degree holders know how to define educational planning; and the education administrators who have

undergraduate degrees do not know the educational planning concept as a whole. The definitions of two education administrators who were postgraduate degree holders are as follows; A2 *“educational planning means calculating the inputs and outcomes for the purpose of achieving the educational targets by the state”*; and A7 defined it as *“determining our present status and what we should do in order to reach our goals in education”*.

3.3 Planning in School Management

The participants answered the question *“How do you make planning in school management?”* as follows; *“I prepare student flowchart, I define the number of the classrooms and teachers”* (A7), *“I compare the targets, aims, the point to be reached and the data at hand in terms of the vision and mission of the school. The future works are defined”* (A2), *“students are registered, classrooms are determined, the classrooms are distributed to the teachers in the teachers” board* (A4, A6). *“The normative employment charts of teachers are prepared in the light of the number of the students that will be registered at the school, and if more teachers are needed, this is reported to the Directorate of MoNE”* (A5), *“the achievements (and the failures in doing so) in the targets in the previous year are determined. It is determined why the targets of the previous year were not achieved, and the new plan is made in the light of these data”* (A3); *“a roadmap is prepared to eliminate the missing points in the budget of the school, the number of the teachers, and the classrooms”* (A8, A10). *Firstly, the team that will run the works for the preparation of educational plan is formed. This team takes the photographs of the school, obtain relevant data, determines the present status of the school, and defines the satisfaction and expectations of the teachers, students and parents”* (A9).

In the light of these statements, it is possible to claim that the education administrators who hold a postgraduate degree are adequate in planning the educational activities; however, the managers with undergraduate degree do not have adequate information on preparing and running an educational planning in their schools.

The viewpoints of two educational managers who hold postgraduate degrees on educational planning activities are as follows; *“calculating the number of the students who possible will arrive and who will graduate from the school; determining whether there will be a need for classrooms in future years or whether there will be free classrooms; determining whether teachers will be more than needed in certain branches or whether there will be more need for teachers from certain branches; will the rooms and management areas be adequate or not; and making predictions on these issues for the purpose of educational planning”* (A7). A9 said *“firstly a team is formed to run the educational planning works at school. This team takes the photographs of the school, obtains data on the present status of the school and determines the satisfactions and expectations of the teachers, students and parents. Then, the team compares the targets, aims, and the present data in terms of the vision and mission of the school, and defines the work to be done. In this way, the plan and roadmap for the following year will be obtained. The achievements and failures of the academic year are defined and precautions are taken in the respect”*.

3.4 The Status of Receiving Training on Educational Planning

In the question *“have you ever received any training on educational planning?”*, educational managers who had 1-5 years' experience stated that they did not have any in-service training” (A1, A5, A8, A10); and *“those participants who had postgraduate degree stated that they received in-service trainings”* (A2, A7, A9). It is possible to claim that the managers who had 10+ years of experience and those with postgraduate degrees received adequate training on educational planning; however, the managers who are new in their positions did not have any training on this field. In addition, it is also possible to claim that education managers must receive training on the management processes after they are appointed as managers.

3.5. Problems Related with Education Planning in Our Country

The question *“In your opinion, what are the problems about educational planning?”* was asked to the education managers, and the answers were as follows; *“the authorities in the ministry and in other educational institutions do not know educational planning”* (A2), *when the number of students in classes and the number of schools are considered in specific, and when the number of unemployed people is considered in general, the rate of educational planning becomes obvious* (A6); *“I do not think that education planning is performed in the way it should be”* (A1, A3); *“unfortunately, educational planning remains on paper in many institutions mainly in the Ministry”* (A7); *“educational planning is run with daily orders and instructions, last-minute works are required without any planning”* (A9); *“first of all, the managers in the country, and the managers in education must believe in the importance of planning”* (A8); *“the teachers who are not appointed to any posts are the result of lack of an educational planning”* (A5); *“the conversion of general high schools into Anatolian High Schools is the result of an unplanned action”* (A4); *“many of our students did not make any preferences for university departments because they know that they will be unemployed when they graduate”* (A10). It is possible to claim that starting from the senior-level education managers, towards the lower-level managers in educational institutions, planning is not adequate and effective, and the strategic plans remain on paper without applying them in real life.

3.6. The Benefits of Planning in Education

The question *“In your opinion, what may the benefits of making an educational planning be?”* was asked to the education managers, and the answers were as follows; *“the wasting of resources will be avoided”* (A2); *“adequate schools are built, teachers are employed”*, (A3); *“the unemployment of the trained people is avoided”* (A6, A8); *“everybody can work in accordance with the training they receive”* (A5); *“we can have well-trained human resources”* (A1); *“it ensures rational and economic behaviors”* (A7); *“it ensures that the required effort is made to reach the defined targets”* (A9); *“it ensures that the works produce agreeable results and are applicable”* (A10); *“it ensures that the available materials and human resources are used well, and we spend our times in a better manner”* (A4). All of the education managers who participated in the study mentioned that making an education planning would be beneficial for the society and for the individual. However, it is possible to

claim that the majority of the educational managers do not know how to make an educational planning.

4. Results, Discussion and Conclusion

This study, which aimed to determine the viewpoints of educational managers on educational planning, was conducted with face-to-face detailed interviews with ten educational managers. Some results were obtained in the study about the viewpoints of the educational managers on the planning concept, educational planning concept, activities included in the educational planning at schools, and the problems related with educational planning in our country.

It was observed in the study that the educational managers do not have adequate information on educational planning. However, it is possible to claim that the educational managers who hold a postgraduate degree on education have dominance in the concept of educational planning. If the candidates that have postgraduate degree are preferred in appointing educational managers, educational planning may function better. Although the knowledge of educational managers on educational planning is inadequate, it is possible to claim that they consider educational planning in a positive way. Memduhoğlu & Uçar (2012) and Küçüker (2016) reported similar results in their studies conducted on strategic planning.

It was observed that educational planning works are planned at teachers' boards at schools in school management. There are several education administrators who prepare the educational planning by preparing a student flowchart. In general, managers plan the number of the students and teachers, the number of classrooms at school, the income and expenses of the schools, and the compulsory number of teachers at schools. In actual fact, there are strategic planning made with the demand of the City/County MoNE Directorates on paper; however, it was mentioned by managers that they are not functional. In addition, it is also possible to claim that education managers make a team consisting of teachers do the planning at schools, and this is performed by making some minor changes on the plan that belong to previous years. Küçüker (2016) conducted a study and reported a similar result showing that teachers make a planning by filling in a standard form.

It was concluded in the present study that aside from the education administrators who had post-graduate degree education on educational planning and those with ten years and over experience, no education administrators had received any in-service training. If the educational managers are selected from among the candidates with postgraduate level education, this problem may be overcome. Or in-service trainings may be provided to the educational managers whose experience is below ten years. The problems experienced in the field of educational planning are mentioned by the participants as follows. 1. Educational managers starting from the top level to the lowest level are not adequate in educational planning. 2. No realistic educational planning is made in our country. The justification for this may be considered as the number of the unemployed people who receive undergraduate degrees, and the

number of teachers who are not appointed to any posts after graduation. In addition, Kiraz (2014) reported in a doctorate thesis that the reason of unemployment in educated people stemmed from the lack of an educational planning. 3. Since the educational plans are not applicable, they remain on paper. 4. Unplanned education has become a "plan". 5. Educational managers do not believe in the importance of planning. Bayram conducted a postgraduate thesis study in 2009 and reported that educational managers did not believe in the applicability of a strategic plan. 6. The society does not consider education as valuable at an adequate level. Especially in 2017 university preference processes, it was reported that a total of 852.000 candidates did not make any preferences (OSYM, 2017). It is interpreted as the university education is not considered as valuable enough by candidates and their families.

Educational managers point out to the importance of an applicable educational plan. The participants stated that the educational plan had the following benefits; "1. It provides saving in material and human resources; 2. It provides that schools are built and teachers are raised in the amount that is needed; 3. Everybody works in the field of their own educational fields; 4. It provides rational and economic behaviors; 5. It provides that achievable targets are set and are achieved; 6. It ensures that the educational works are in accordance and results are obtained from them".

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References

- Âdem M. (1997). Eğitim planlaması. İkinci Basım, Ankara, Turkey
- Adem M. (2008). Eğitim planlaması. Ankara, Turkey
- Altundemir M. E (2012). Kalkınma planlarından eğitime bakış: kamusal mallar teorisi perspektifinden. The Journal of Knowledge Economy & Knowledge Management. Volume: VII Spring
- Baker C., Wuest J., Stern, P. N. (1992). Method slurring: the grounded theory/phenomenology example. Journal of Advanced Nursing, 17, 1355-1360.
- Bayram A. (2009). Ankara İl Milli Eğitim Müdürlüğü'nde stratejik planlamanın uygulanmasına ilişkin ilköğretim müfettişi, yönetici ve diğer çalışanların görüşleri. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Ankara Üniversitesi
- Burashioğlu Z. (1994). Okul yönetiminde yeni yapı ve davranış. Ankara, Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2016). Bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri. Ankara, Turkey

- Coombs P. H. (1973). Eğitim planlaması nedir? (Çev. Cemal Mihçioğlu), İstanbul, Turkey
- Ersoy F. (2016). Eğitimde nitel araştırma desenleri. Ankara, Turkey
- Jasper M. A. (1994). Issues in phenomenology for researchers of nursing. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 19, 309- 314.
- Karakütük K. (2001). Lisansüstü öğretimin planlanması. Ankara, Turkey
- Karakütük K. (2016). Eğitim planlaması. Ankara, Turkey
- Karakütük K. (2017). Eğitim planlaması. Ankara, Turkey
- Küçükler E. (2016). Okul Müdürlerinin Planlama Etkinlikleri ve Stratejik Planlamada Karşılaşılan Sorunlar. *Kastamonu Eğitim Dergisi Cilt:24 No:2*
- Kiraz Z. (2014). Türkiye'de öğretmenlerin işsizliği ve ataması yapılmayan öğretmenler hareketinin çözümlemesi. Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi. Ankara Üniversitesi
- Memduhoğlu H. B., Uçar İ. H. (2012). Yönetici ve Öğretmenlerin Stratejik Planlama Algısı ve Okullarda Mevcut Stratejik Planlama Uygulamalarının Değerlendirilmesi. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi, Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 12 (23), 234-256.
- Miller S. (2003). Analysis of Phenomenological Data Generated with Children as Research Participants. *Nurse Researcher*, 10 (4), 68-82.
- Patel R. M. (2002). Phenomenoloji: History, its methodological assumptions and application. Mini-dissertation. Unpublished master's thesis, Rand Afrikaans University.
- Smith J. A., Eatough V. (2007). Interpretative phenomenological analysis, in Lyons E. & Coyle, A. *Analysing Qualitative Data in Psychology*, pp: 35-64, London, England
- Şekerciler S. A. (2015). Nitel araştırma. Ankara, Turkey
- Yıldırım A., Şimşek H. (2006). Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri. Ankara, Turkey
- <http://dokuman.osym.gov.tr/pdfdokuman/2017/OSYS/YER/YSay%C4%B1sal%20Bilgiler15082017.pdf>.

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